

Harbingers of Turmoil? The Effect of Foreign Fighters on Insurgent Splintering

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Abstract

Despite a remarkable influx of foreign fighters into the Syrian civil war, their influence on insurgent cohesion remains an understudied phenomenon. The existing studies on the influence of foreign fighters on insurgent cohesion come to contradictory findings, all of which, I argue, are driven by the lack of systematic analysis. Examining over four hundred insurgent organizations since 1946, I find no support for the prominent argument that the influx of foreign fighters makes an insurgent organization more prone to splintering. Neither do organizational and ideological characteristics of the insurgency coupled with foreign fighters prevent splintering. Consistent with the more general research on organizational splits within political organizations, I find that centralized insurgent organizations hinder splintering when they do not host foreign fighters.

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Introduction

Does the influx of foreign fighters make insurgent groups more prone to splintering? Some insurgent organizations such as the Chechen Republic, the Moro Islamic Liberation Front, and Al-Mahdi Army have hosted foreign fighters to the detriment of their cohesion, while other similar hosts such as Daesh, Al-Shabaab, and the Revolutionary United Front in Sierra Leone have avoided splintering. The few studies that analyze this question come to contradictory findings. On the one hand, some find that foreign fighters may sow division within insurgent ranks because they nurture values and goals that are at odds with organizations they join.¹ Other studies suggest that the impact of foreign fighters on insurgent cohesion may be uneven and mediated by internal features such as centralization or ideology.²

This paper aims to disentangle these differences in the literature on foreign fighters and civil war dynamics. Existing research makes inferences about the influence of foreign fighters on insurgent cohesion based on a few case studies. Rather than develop a theory of insurgent splintering the aim of this paper is to contribute to the debate by systematically examining the determinants of splintering for all insurgent groups engaged in civil conflicts from 1946 until 2013. Splinter groups tend to embrace the deadliest tactics such as suicide

¹See, for example: Kristin M. Bakke, "Help wanted? The mixed record of foreign fighters in domestic insurgencies," *International Security* 38, no. 4 (2014): 150–187; Ben Rich and Dara Conduit, "The impact of jihadist foreign fighters on indigenous secular-nationalist causes: Contrasting Chechnya and Syria," *Studies in Conflict & Terrorism* 38, no. 2 (2015): 113–131; Jeni Mitchell, "The contradictory effects of ideology on Jihadist war-fighting: The Bosnia Precedent," *Studies in Conflict & Terrorism* 31, no. 9 (2008): 808–828; Barak Mendelsohn, "Foreign fighters—recent trends," *Orbis* 55, no. 2 (2011): 189–202; Kristin M. Bakke, "Copying and learning from outsiders? Assessing diffusion from transnational insurgents in the Chechen wars," in: Jeffrey Checke, *Transnational Dynamics of Civil War* (Cambridge University Press, 2013): 31–63; Pauline L. Moore, "When Do Ties Bind? Foreign Fighters, Social Embeddedness, and Combatant Repertoires of Behavior during Civil War," PhD dissertation (University of Denver, 2019).

²See, for example: Scott Gates and Sukanya Podder, "Social media, recruitment, allegiance and the Islamic State," *Perspectives on Terrorism* 9, no. 4 (2015): 107–116; Scott Gates and Ragnhild Nordås, "Recruitment, Retention and Religion in Rebel Groups," In Workshop 'Peace, Conflict, and Development', Centre for the Study of Equality, Social Organization (ESOP), University of Oslo, vol. 24. (2015); Vera Mironova, *From Freedom Fighters to Jihadists: Human Resources of Non-State Armed Groups* (Oxford University Press, 2019).

bombing, undermine peace efforts, and commit atrocities as a way of outbidding their parent organization. Analyzing whether and to what extent foreign fighters contribute to splintering— especially as established terrorist groups give birth to new outfits, terrorism— is, therefore, paramount for both the academic and policy world.

The findings question existing knowledge on the influence of foreign fighters on domestic insurgency in that I find no support for the prominent explanation that the presence of foreign fighters leads to splintering of their insurgent hosts. Neither do I find support for the counter-argument that more centralized organizations can accommodate foreign fighters without splintering. Rather, more centralization alone is sufficient to prevent splintering irrespective of foreign fighters. Foreign fighters are, therefore, neither beneficial nor detrimental to insurgent cohesion as the existing debate suggests.

The Literature on Foreign Fighters and Splintering

Insurgent splintering is endemic in civil conflicts and occurs when a group breaks off from a parent organization under a different leadership and name.³ Splinter groups tend to embrace the deadliest tactics such as suicide bombing,⁴ undermine peace efforts,⁵ and commit atrocities as a way of outbidding their parent organization.⁶ Among the determinants of splintering, some explanations point to the lack of solid social or organizational foundation.⁷ Other theories examine schisms in the shadow of state power to argue that

³Hanne Fjelde and Desirée Nilsson, "The rise of rebel contenders: Barriers to entry and fragmentation in civil wars," *Journal of Peace Research* 55, no. 5 (2018): 551–565.

⁴Mia M. Bloom, "Palestinian suicide bombing: Public support, market share, and outbidding," *Political Science Quarterly* 119, no. 1 (2004): 61–88.

⁵Stephen J. Stedman, "Spoiler problems in peace processes," *International Security* 22, no. 2 (1997): 5–53; Audrey K. Cronin, "How al-Qaida ends: The decline and demise of terrorist groups," *International Security* 31, no. 1 (2006): 7–48; David E. Cunningham, "Veto players and civil war duration," *American Journal of Political Science* 50, no. 4 (2006): 875–892.

⁶Andrew H. Kydd and Barbara F. Walter, "The strategies of terrorism," *International Security* 31, no. 1 (2006): 49–80.

⁷See, for example: Victor Asal, Mitchell Brown, and Angela Dalton, "Why split? Organizational splits among ethnopolitical organizations in the Middle East," *Journal of Conflict Resolution* 56, no. 1 (2012): 94–117; Paul D. Kenny, "Structural integrity and cohesion in insurgent organizations: Evidence from protracted conflicts in Ireland and Burma," *International Studies Review* 12, no. 4 (2010): 533–555; Wendy Pearlman, *Violence*,

state repression or sponsorship incites factionalism.⁸ Although many contemporary civil conflicts are a hotbed of actors, resources, and events that span national boundaries, there is a dearth of studies that explore how transnational linkages influence splintering.

Emerging in-depth studies on foreign fighters in civil conflicts shed more light on the transnational origins of splintering. Yet, these studies offer contradictory findings on the influence of foreign fighters on splintering of insurgent organizations they join. While some studies demonstrate that foreign fighters serve as an asset to their hosts,⁹ others show that the very qualities that make foreign fighter attractive may ultimately harm the organizational cohesion of domestic insurgents.¹⁰ Foreign fighters may arguably instigate splits within domestic insurgency when they are either too opportunistic or overzealous. Greedy fighters may be exiled when they engage in shirking, embezzlement or defiance.¹¹ Overzealous foreign fighters, on the other hand, tend to impose radical and often alien ideas on their local host organization and population.¹² Furthermore, radical foreign fighters devoid their host of popular support when they abuse the local population. Thus, foreign

Nonviolence, and the Palestinian National Movement (Cambridge University Press, 2011); Paul Staniland, "Organizing insurgency: Networks, resources, and rebellion in South Asia." *International Security* 37, no. 1 (2012): 142–177; Austin Doctor, "A Motion of No Confidence: Leadership and Rebel Fragmentation," *Journal of Global Security Studies*, forthcoming; Evan Perkoski, "Internal Politics and the Fragmentation of Armed Groups," *International Studies Quarterly*, forthcoming (2019).

⁸Fotini Christia, *Alliance Formation in Civil Wars* (Cambridge University Press, 2012); Hanne Fjelde and Desirée Nilsson, "Rebels against rebels: Explaining violence between rebel groups," *Journal of Conflict Resolution* 56, no. 4 (2012): 604–628; Lee Seymour, Kristin M. Bakke, and Kathleen Gallagher Cunningham, "E pluribus unum, ex uno plures: Competition, violence, and fragmentation in ethnopolitical movements," *Journal of Peace Research* 53, no. 1 (2016): 3–18; Jacob N. Shapiro, *The Terrorist's Dilemma: Managing Violent Covert Organizations* (Princeton University Press, 2013); Paul Staniland, *Networks of Rebellion: Explaining Insurgent Cohesion and Collapse* (Cornell University Press, 2014); Henning Tamm, "Rebel leaders, internal rivals, and external resources: How state sponsors affect insurgent cohesion," *International Studies Quarterly* 60, no. 4 (2016): 599–610; Michael Woldemariam, "Battlefield outcomes and rebel cohesion: Lessons from the Eritrean independence war," *Terrorism and Political Violence* 28, no. 1 (2016): 135–156.

⁹David Malet, *Foreign Fighters: Transnational Identity in Civil Conflicts* (Oxford University Press, 2013); Tiffany S. Chu and Alex Braithwaite, "The impact of foreign fighters on civil conflict outcomes," *Research & Politics* 4, no. 3 (2017): 1–7.

¹⁰See note 1 above.

¹¹Matthew Levitt, "Foreign fighters and their economic impact: A case study of Syria and al-Qaeda in Iraq (AQI)," *Perspectives on Terrorism* 3, no. 3 (2009): 14–24.

¹²Bakke (see note 1 above).

fighters are likely to create divisions between local and foreign factions, making foreign fighter-heavy organizations more vulnerable to splintering.

However, other studies disagree with this view because certain insurgent organizations have remained cohesive despite the influx of foreign fighters. A small set of exploratory case studies examines this variation, but they all come to inconsistent conclusions. On the one hand, some argue that splintering in the wake of foreign fighter influx can be averted if insurgents have a centralized organization in place. Highly centralized organizations have a robust monitoring and sanctioning capacity to deter disgruntled foreign fighters from defection. For instance, leaving Daesh is a costly strategy because anyone caught attempting to break free would be imprisoned or killed.¹³ On the other, ideology might serve as a bulwark against factionalism. The internalization of the ideals of the organization might be so powerful as to diminish a slightest preference for misbehavior and defection.¹⁴ Choosing defection over obedience comes at a cost of exclusion, which is a strong sanctioning mechanism in organizations built on solidarity.¹⁵ The most extreme ideologies should have the strongest bonds and, consequently impose the highest costs on defectors.

What does one make of these various findings? This paper aims to improve on existing research methods in order to better understand whether foreign fighters contribute to insurgent splintering. Each of the existing studies highlights important pathways from the recruitment of foreign fighters to insurgent splintering. However, each also has methodological limitations that I aim to remedy.

A major reason for some of the contradictory results in existing literature lies with a dominant focus on exploratory and single-case studies.¹⁶ Analyzing splintering through

¹³Gates and Podder (see note 2 above): 112.

¹⁴Gates and Nordås (see note 2 above).

¹⁵Gates and Podder (see note 2 above): 111.

¹⁶Bart Schuurman, "Research on terrorism, 2007–2016: a review of data, methods, and authorship," *Terrorism and Political Violence* (2018): 1–16.

small-N is illustrative; however, given the complexity of the phenomenon as well as the myriad of variables at play, it is insufficient to make inferences about the causes of splintering based on a few case studies.¹⁷ Moreover, these studies are vulnerable to selection bias as none of them compares the cohesion of insurgent groups with foreign fighters to those composed of local recruits. Finally, any effect of foreign fighters on insurgent cohesion might be confounded by other variables such as organizational and conflict features.

This paper attempts to improve on existing studies by employing a large-N design to examine whether insurgent organizations who host foreign fighters are more associated with organizational schisms than those without foreign fighters. The large-N study allows for systematic testing of this important question in an unbiased fashion. The inclusion of other variables pertaining to conflict dynamics and organizational characteristics provides a more robust analysis. Additionally, matching techniques are used to address potential endogeneity concerns because the influx of foreign fighters might be affected by prior organizational and conflict features.

Hypotheses on Foreign Fighters and Splintering

Does the presence of foreign fighters make insurgent groups more prone to splintering? As noted above, the existing literature comes to often conflicting conclusions. These are reflected in two arguments: those that theorize a linkage between foreign fighters and splintering versus those that suggest a conditional relationship between foreign fighters and splintering.

Foreign Fighters Fuel Splintering

Some studies demonstrate that foreign fighters might sow discord in insurgent ranks when they are poorly attuned to local material and social conditions. First, the influx of opportunistic fighters can translate into financial losses for the domestic insurgents

¹⁷Asal, Brown and Dalton make a similar case for exploring organizational schisms in ethnopolitical organizations in the Middle East through a large-N study. See: Asal, Brown and Dalton (see note 7 above).

due to the embezzlement of organizational funds. For example, Al-Qaeda in Iraq (AQI) has experienced skimming of funds from affiliated groups in Sudan who were apparently displeased with low salaries.¹⁸ Second, battle-hardened outsiders might use violence indiscriminately against civilians.¹⁹ This brutalization of civilians may, in turn, pit the local population against the domestic insurgency, create a rift between the foreign fighters and the local leadership, and, ultimately, spell an end to the rebellion.

Another way to plant divisions into the insurgency is through the transmission of ideas, goals and plans that are at odds with domestic insurgents. Radical ideas may boost troop morale but their discord with the character of the local struggle may also lead to strategic setbacks.²⁰ Even worse, overzealous ideas could cause splintering of domestic insurgents. Kristin Bakke shows that foreign fighters from the Middle East and North Africa who joined the Chechen insurgency had Wahhabi convictions that clashed with a more secular vision shared by the domestic insurgency and local population.²¹ In an attempt to spread alien understanding among the Chechen insurgents and civilians, foreign fighters instigated a split between the nationalist and Islamist wing of the insurgent organization. The formation of the Caucasus Emirate led by the Islamist leadership and the subsequent emergence of the pro-Kremlin organization of defectors marked the final stage of the Chechen splintering. Similarly, Rich and Conduit compare foreign militants in Chechen and Syrian insurgencies to conclude that foreign fighters might create divisions within the domestic organizations they join.²² Such a pattern appears to be present in the birth of Al-Nusra from Al-Qaeda due to the marginalization of Syrians in the parent organization.²³

¹⁸Levitt (see note 11 above).

¹⁹Mendelsohn (see note 1 above); Bakke (see note 1 above); Bakke (see note 1 above); Moore (see note 1 above).

²⁰Mitchell (see note 1 above).

²¹Bakke (see note 1 above).

²²Rich and Conduit (see note 1 above).

²³Joseph Felter and Brian Fishman, "Al-Qa'ida's Foreign Fighters in Iraq: A First Look at the Sinjar Records," (Military Academy West Point NY Combating Terrorism Center, 2007).

In sum, this logic holds that the recruitment of foreign fighters into insurgency is likely to incite splintering in the domestic insurgency:

Hypothesis 1: The presence of foreign fighters in insurgent organization is likely to lead to insurgent splintering.

Centralization Prevents Splintering

Since insurgent organizations lack information about the incoming recruits they might attract incompetent, opportunistic, overzealous or treacherous foreign fighters.²⁴ Once recruits are deployed to the battlefield, they might shirk their duties, defy orders or even turn against their leadership.²⁵ To limit agency slack, insurgent leadership develops screening, monitoring, and sanctioning mechanisms through such institutional designs as hierarchy, bureaucratic apparatus, and standard operating procedures that are inherent in centralized organizations.²⁶ Recognizing the benefit of centralized leadership in insurgent organizations Rich and Conduit argue that foreign fighters who were integrated into the military hierarchy had a much lower impact on internal cohesion than those that were allowed to operate as autonomous units, as was evident in Chechnya and Syria.²⁷ Foreign combatants who were allowed to create subgroups around their own ethnic communities in Jabhat al-Nusra and ISIS tended to bypass central command and make essential decisions on their own.²⁸ Gates and Podder suggest that the presence of extensive bureaucracy may help curtail such insubordination.²⁹ These insights lead to the following hypothesis:

Hypothesis 2a: The presence of foreign fighters in combination with centralized organization is less likely to lead to insurgent splintering.

²⁴Idean Salehyan, "The delegation of war to rebel organizations," *Journal of Conflict Resolution* 54, no. 3 (2010): 493–515.

²⁵Shapiro (see note 8 above).

²⁶Abdulkader H. Sinno, *Organizations at War in Afghanistan and Beyond* (Cornell University Press, 2011).

²⁷Rich and Conduit (see note 1 above): 125.

²⁸Mironova (see note 2 above): 143–144).

²⁹Gates and Podder (see note 2 above): 111.

Religious Groups Are More Cohesive

Insurgent leadership can use religious beliefs to buttress organizational cohesion by credibly threatening to use the most severe punishment against defectors. A reference to God's will as a justification for penalty may augment the perception that the punishment for disobedience will be carried out.³⁰ For most extreme members, this warrants certainty of punishment that extends to afterlife. If punishment for going against group leadership is certain and extended to afterlife, then internalized beliefs might serve as a strong deterrent against splintering.

Some rebel groups such as Jabhat-al-Nusra and Ahrar al-Sham have designed code of conduct based on their interpretation of the holy books.³¹ Enforcement of such a code varies from symbolic penalty such as humiliation and loss of honor to physical punishment, expulsion, and death.³² Rebel groups could, therefore, use dogma as a warning against future transgressions as well as a tool for aligning the preferences between the leadership and rank-and-file.³³ If this logic holds, one should expect that despite the influx of foreign fighters, religious organizations are more likely to avoid factionalism. This leads to the following hypothesis:

Hypothesis 2b: The presence of foreign fighters in combination with religious character of insurgency is less likely to lead to insurgent splintering.

Data and Research Design

To test whether foreign fighters affect splintering of insurgent organizations they join, I run a series of tests on an UCDP Armed Conflict Dataset with insurgent organization as

³⁰Gates and Nordås (see note 2 above): 19.

³¹Mironova (see note 2 above): 89–93).

³²Gates and Podder (see note 2 above): 112.

³³Daniel Byman and Sarah E. Kreps, "Agents of destruction? Applying principal-agent analysis to state-sponsored terrorism," *International Studies Perspectives* 11, no. 1 (2010): 1–18.

the main unit of analysis.³⁴ The UCDP includes insurgencies that resulted in at least 25 fatalities in clashes with the government. This yields 462 insurgent organizations for the period 1946–2013.

This paper analyzes the factionalism in insurgent organizations amid an influx of foreign fighters. To measure splintering, I use the UCDP Actor Dataset v. 2.2-2015, which defines the phenomenon as a "non-state actor [that] was formed by breaking away from an actor that has also been registered in UCDP data."³⁵ This dataset also offers information on the parent organization from which an actor broke away, and that allows for determining whether an insurgent organization experienced splintering in the past. Insurgent organizations that experienced splintering in the past were coded 1 and those that did not were coded 0. Overall, splintering appears to be rare among insurgent organizations as the data yield a total of 68 organizations that experienced splintering and 394 that did not.

The main independent variable is whether foreign fighters joined an insurgent organization in their fight against the government. This variable comes in the binary form, and it is coded 1 if foreign individuals took part in local insurgent organization and 0 otherwise.³⁶ This measure is limited in several ways that might cause omitted-variable bias and reversed causality. First, the data lack information on the size of foreign fighters. While the existing theories generally have no expectations about the size of the foreign contingent, insurgent organizations with large contingents of foreign fighters might reasonably be more vulnerable to factionalism than organizations with a handful of foreign combatants. In this case, the share of foreign fighters in an organization might explain the variation in splintering better than the presence of foreign fighters. It is possible, however, that Malet

³⁴Lotta Themnér and Peter Wallensteen, "Armed Conflicts, 1946–2011," *Journal of Peace Research* 49, no. 4 (2012): 565–575.

³⁵Pettersson, Therése, and Peter Wallensteen. "Armed conflicts, 1946–2014," *Journal of Peace Research* 52, no. 4 (2015): 536–550.

³⁶David Malet, "Foreign fighter data: 2016 version," (2016) data retrieved from: http://davidmalet.com/The_Foreign_Fighter_Project.php.

takes into account only instances with a significant presence of foreign fighters. This might partly address the omitted variable bias. Second, the data include no information on the timing of the foreign fighter influx. Since foreigners may arrive in the wake of splintering, it is possible that in some cases splintering precedes the influx of foreign combatants. According to existing studies, it appears that foreign fighters usually join organizations in their formative years.

Other explanatory variables are conditional on the presence of foreign fighters and include the level of insurgent centralization and religious ideology. To measure centralization I use the EACD dataset,³⁷ which indicates the extent to which the leadership of insurgent organization controls the rank-and-file. This measure is composed of four values (none, low, medium and high) but I collapse the first two into one to indicate the lack of centralization or 0, while the latter two are aggregated into a single value and indicate the existence of centralization or 1. Finally, whether an insurgent organization claims to fight in the name of religion is measured using the Religion and Armed Conflict (RELAC) dataset.³⁸ This dataset measures religious insurgencies as organizations that fight over religious issues against the government and claim adherence to a certain religion.³⁹

This paper considers a series of control variables likely to affect splintering. Because some studies show that insurgents might splinter when they incur significant military losses,⁴⁰ while others demonstrate that repression might unify groups,⁴¹ it is necessary to

³⁷David E. Cunningham, Kristian Skrede Gleditsch, and Idean Salehyan, "It takes two: A dyadic analysis of civil war duration and outcome," *Journal of Conflict Resolution* 53, no. 4 (2009): 570–597.

³⁸Isak Svensson and Desirée Nilsson, "Disputes over the divine: Introducing the religion and armed conflict (RELAC) data, 1975 to 2015," *Journal of Conflict Resolution* 62, no. 5 (2018): 1127–1148.

³⁹Since the dataset covers the period from 1975 until 2015, I code the period before 1975 using a dataset by Polo and Gleditsch who measure religious outfits as organizations that not only claim to represent a religion but also seek to organize the state in accordance with religious teachings. See: Sara Polo and Kristian Skrede Gleditsch, "Twisting arms and sending messages: Terrorist tactics in civil war," *Journal of Peace Research* 53, no. 6 (2016): 815–829.

⁴⁰Christia (see note 8 above); Woldemariam (see note 8 above); Camber T. Warren and Kevin K. Troy, "Explaining violent intra-ethnic conflict: Group fragmentation in the shadow of state power," *Journal of Conflict Resolution* 59, no. 3 (2015): 484–509.

⁴¹Asal, Brown and Dalton (see note 7 above); Theodore McLauchlin and Wendy Pearlman, "Out-group

control for conflict intensity. The variable intensity is coded 1 if the conflict claimed at least 1,000 battle-related deaths and 0 otherwise. This variable originates from the UCDP Actor Dataset v. 2.2-2015. Another important control is external involvement because external states may influence both the resources and the preferences of the warring sides, and accelerate insurgent splintering.⁴² Henning Tamm shows that splintering occurs when state sponsors divide their support among rebel leaders and internal rivals.⁴³ If this logic holds, foreign support should be associated with a greater likelihood of splintering. This variable indicates whether an insurgent group received external state support in the past (coded 1) or not (coded 0) and comes from the EACD dataset. Next, longer conflicts might consume insurgent capabilities, leading to defection and factionalism. Duration indicates the number of years since the insurgent organization carried out violence for the first time. Finally, multiparty conflicts might allow for the rise of contenders through internecine fighting with other insurgent organizations. This variable signifies the presence (coded 1) or absence (coded 0) of other outfits in the same conflict.

Matching and the Effects of Foreign Fighters

Whether foreign fighters enter a conflict might already be determined by the nature of the organizations they join. On the demand side, it is possible that weaker outfits recruit foreign combatants because they lack manpower. On the supply side, foreign fighters might face lower barriers to entry in organizations with weak central leadership. In both instances, for the identical reasons that an insurgent organization lacking manpower or strong leadership might seek foreign fighters, a powerful insurgent organization might not. To address the possibility that insurgent cohesion influences foreign fighters, I use matching analysis to reduce concerns on endogeneity bias.

conflict, in-group unity? Exploring the effect of repression on intramovement cooperation," *Journal of Conflict Resolution* 56, no. 1 (2012): 41–66.

⁴²Seymour (see note 8 above).

⁴³Tamm (see note 8 above).

The matching method transforms the data to resemble experimental data by pruning observations from the sample that have no close matches on pre-treatment covariates in both the treated and control groups. Matching creates a sample of variables with similar values in the treatment group (insurgents with foreign fighters) and control group (insurgents without foreign fighters), making insurgents similarly likely to experience splintering in the absence of foreign fighters. This lowers the risk that foreign fighters are correlated with other variables.

In this paper, I use coarsened exact matching (CEM) to perform the matching method.⁴⁴ The CEM is a nonparametric method of pre-processing data that strikes the balance between the treated and control groups by coarsening observations into values of the treatment variable (foreign fighters) on the basis of control variables. Next, the CEM algorithm sorts all observations into strata, preserving only those that include observations from both treatment and control groups. Any stratum that does not include at least one treated and one control unit is pruned from the sample. Post-matching analysis includes weights that adjust observations in the control group within each stratum, which are weighted to equal the number of treated units in that stratum.

There are a few variables that could drive the influx of foreign fighters based on the outfit characteristics. First, weaker groups might attract foreign fighters because they lack manpower. Using the EACD measurement of group strength, outfits that have parity with or are stronger than the government are coded 1 while those that are weaker than the government are coded 0. Second, centralized organizations should be more capable of attracting foreign fighters as they have developed bureaucratic apparatus necessary for recruitment. This variable measures the extent to which the leadership of insurgent organization controls the rank-and-file and comes from the EACD dataset. Third, foreign

⁴⁴Stefano M. Iacus, Gary King, and Giuseppe Porro, "Causal inference without balance checking: Coarsened exact matching," *Political Analysis* 20, no. 1 (2012): 1–24.

fighters might be attracted to organizations that foster the most extreme views. Given that religion is often misused for the creation of most exclusionary and divisive forms of ideology, I code this variable 1 if an outfit claims to promote a religion and 0 otherwise based on the Religion and Armed Conflict (RELAC) dataset. Finally, foreign fighters might be attracted to more durable and intense conflicts. Intensity is coded 1 if the conflict claimed at least 1,000 battle-related deaths and 0 otherwise. This variable originates from the UCDP Actor Dataset v. 2.2-2015. I use cutpoints to coarsen the variables used for matching analysis, with dummy variables coarsened into two categories, and duration into five categories.⁴⁵ The CEM procedure identified 95 matched strata for 348 observations remaining in the matched sample. For each observation, the proportion of treated observations to controls in the strata is used to create a CEM weight, and these weights are included in post-matching analyses.

Empirical Analysis

Figure 1 summarizes the results for the full model with matching.⁴⁶ These results are displayed separately for each of the hypotheses. Model 1 tests the expectation that, all else being equal, the presence of foreign fighters should be more likely to lead to splintering (H1). The first model presents findings for the dichotomous foreign fighter variable and control variables. Contrary to H1, I find that foreign fighters are neither more or less likely to fuel splintering of organizations they join. The variable measuring the presence of foreign

⁴⁵I tested different levels of coarsening, but they did not significantly alter the results.

⁴⁶The logistic regression was fit using full Bayesian estimation via Markov Chain Monte Carlo as implemented in the `rstanarm` package for the R language. See: Jonah Gabry and Ben Goodrich. "rstanarm: Bayesian applied regression modeling via Stan," *R package version 2*, no. 1 (2016); W. N. Venables, D. M. Smith, and R CORE TEAM. "An introduction to R, 2017," available at: <https://cran.r-project.org/doc/manuals/r-release/R-intro.pdf> (2017). Each model was fit running four separate chains, each for one thousand warm-up and two thousand sampling iterations. Convergence was assessed using the Gelman-Rubin \hat{R} diagnostic. See: Andrew Gelman and Donald B. Rubin, "Inference from iterative simulation using multiple sequences," *Statistical science* 7, no. 4 (1992): 457–472. Following the American Statistical Association's suggestion to avoid p-values in favor of other approaches, I present coefficient estimates with credible intervals. See: Ronald L. Wasserstein and Nicole A. Lazar, "The ASA's statement on p-values: context, process, and purpose," *The American Statistician* 70, no. 2 (2016): 129–133.

fighters is in the expected positive direction but the size of the effect is marginal and the uncertainty around the estimate is too large to yield practical importance.

Similarly, substantive effects in Figure 2 show that insurgent groups are marginally more likely to experience splintering than those without foreign combatants. The mean predicted probability of splintering in the presence of foreign fighters is 0.19 while the probability of splintering without foreign fighters is 0.15. Contrary to Bakke and other authors, therefore, this paper finds no strong relationship between foreign fighters and insurgent splintering. This is an unexpected result given the predictions in the existing literature that foreign fighters should undermine insurgent cohesion. The findings instead paint a more careful picture of insurgent cohesion—one in which foreign fighters have a far limited impact on organizational dynamics. This limited impact may be due to greater ability of some insurgent organizations to incorporate foreign fighters into their command chain.

Yet, the expectation that the presence of foreign fighters moderated by more centralized leadership should be less likely to lead to fragmentation (H2a) does not receive empirical support in Model 2. The second model computes the probability of splintering as a function of the interaction between the presence of foreign fighters and centralization, and control variables. Contrary to H2a, the interaction term, *Foreign Fighters x Centralized*, is positive but insignificant, indicating that the presence of centralized organization and foreign fighters has no effect on splintering. In contrast, the effect of centralized organization on splintering when there are no foreign fighters is largely negative. This means that centralized organizations might be more cohesive if they recruit local combatants. This result is in line with Assal, Brown and Dalton who find that more centralized ethno-political organizations are less prone to splintering than decentralized outfits. Finally, religious affinities in combination with foreign fighters do not bode so well either. Model 3 shows the regression results for the hypothesis that foreign fighters are less likely to trigger splintering when they join religious organizations (H2b). This hypothesis receives no support as the

Figure 1: Logistic regression for splintering of insurgent organizations, 1946–2013

Note: Bayesian Logistic Regression. The symbol indicates the median point estimate of the posterior distribution, and the solid line displays 90 percent credible intervals. The dashed line is a line of null effect.

Figure 2: Predicted probability of splintering using Model 1

interaction term, `Foreign Fighters x Religious`, has broad intervals that include the line of null effect.

It could be argued that religious ties are not the only indicator of extremist ideology. If extremism denotes black-and-white perception of the social world that strives to exclude some social groups then some secular ideologies might be equally extreme. In additional tests, I replace religious ideology with dummy variables measuring left-wing and ethno-nationalism, respectively,⁴⁷ but the results do not yield any discernible effect on splintering.⁴⁸

Overall, then, foreign fighters have little effect on the prospects for insurgent splintering alone or in interaction with organizational and ideological characteristics. This is a surprising finding given the general expectation in the existing literature that the influx of foreign fighters is likely to be detrimental to organizational cohesion of groups they join.

I ran additional robustness checks to examine whether missing data or the statistical model was affecting results. Missing data was corrected with multiple imputation, creating 100 imputations,⁴⁹ and pre-processed using CEM. As mentioned above, I also tried alternative measures of extremist ideology. Finally, I used multilevel modeling to account for the fact that some insurgent organizations operate in the same conflict, which could potentially bias the results.⁵⁰ None of these robustness checks substantially changed my results.

⁴⁷These measures come from Polo and Gleditsch who code *ethno-nationalist organizations* as those advancing the interest of communal group based on ethnic/separatist othering of distinct communities, and *Marxist-socialist* as groups aiming to establish a socialist state at the expense of the bourgeoisie.

⁴⁸See Figure A1 in the Appendix.

⁴⁹This number is considered very high as the literature recommends only 10 to 50 imputations. Using a higher number is generally good for safety reasons: to be sure that the results hold even when the model is faced with more data. Multiple imputation was carried out using package `mice`. See: Stef van Buuren, Karin Groothuis-Oudshoorn, Alexander Robitzsch, Gerko Vink, Lisa Doove, and Shahab Jolani. "Package 'mice'." Vienna: Comprehensive R Archive Network (2015). The coefficient estimates and standard errors from 100 models were pooled following "Rubin's rule." See: Roderick Little and Donald B. Rubin, *Statistical Analysis with Missing Data*, (Hoboken, NJ: John Wiley & Sons, 2019), at 86–87.

⁵⁰The multilevel model allows coefficients to vary across several levels even where observations are non-independent, correctly modeling correlated error. See: Andrew Gelman and Jennifer Hill, *Data Analysis Using Regression and Multilevel/Hierarchical Models*, (Cambridge University Press, 2006). In this article, I cluster insurgents at the government (country) level.

Conclusion

This paper aimed to make sense of the contradictory findings in the nascent literature on the effects of foreign fighters on the splintering of the insurgent organizations they join. There is a debate in the current literature as to whether and under what conditions foreign fighters have a negative effect on insurgent cohesion. On the one hand, foreign fighters may undermine cohesion when they are too zealous or greedy because they pit the insurgent leadership against the local population. On the other hand, some studies argue that more centralized leadership and strong ideological bonds could prevent splintering amid the influx of foreign fighters. My initial results suggest no support for either of the arguments. The presence of foreign fighters—even when mediated by organizational and ideological characteristics of insurgency—has surprisingly little impact on organizational cohesion. Other aspects of the conflict, whether it is its duration, intensity or fragmentation, have an effect on splintering. Taken together, these findings run contrary to many prominent arguments in the existing literature and show the importance of the methodological fixes employed here.

Research on the effect of incoming foreign fighters on insurgent organizations enables both academics and policy makers to assess the validity of security concerns. The emerging body of work suggests that foreign fighters provide the necessary fuel for insurgency to thrive and grow even when confronted with a capable state. But this study demonstrates that policy makers should not count much on foreign fighters to bring militant organizations down. Neither should they worry that foreign fighters make insurgent organizations more cohesive. Rather policy makers might benefit from exploiting the inner weaknesses of insurgent groups, especially those that already have a decentralized structure.

One aspect of this research that requires more theoretical and empirical attention concerns the possibility of differences in the way insurgent organizations handle foreign

fighters. Previous studies on the Mujahideen in Bosnia, ISIS and Jabhat Al-Nusra find that segregating foreign fighters enables disobedience, shirking and hidden action. It is plausible that the integration of foreign fighters into the hierarchy would mitigate these issues but we lack systematic data to determine such effects.

More generally, the burgeoning research on foreign fighters is in need of deeper theorizing and empirical analysis about the interactions between insurgent organizations, foreign combatants, and the local population. Given the influx of foreign fighters, how do insurgent groups establish or lose their control over the outsiders, and why? Given the salience of the question of foreign fighters in current affairs, further scholarly research on the topic is clearly worthwhile.